

Methodology of Sports and Health Programs through Scandinavian Walking

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Abstract: This article talks about the importance of Nordic walking in optimizing sports rehabilitation programs, its role in maintaining and strengthening public health, and the methodological features of popularizing this sport in our country.

Key points: physical education and sports, skeletal muscles, healthcare, Nordic walking, measurement tools, control tools, monitoring, implementation, control, complex, methodology.

INTRODUCTION

Forming a healthy lifestyle in our society, creating conditions suitable for the population, especially the young generation, to regularly engage in physical education and mass sports, maintaining the health of the population using existing opportunities, increasing the level of physical fitness, the surplus that worries the world health ministry today weight, large-scale works aimed at prevention and rehabilitation of cardiovascular diseases are being carried out. In particular, the development of science in the Republic of Uzbekistan, conducting scientific research in any field and putting the obtained scientific results into practice are considered as the priority directions of the state policy today.

THE PURPOSE OF THE RESEARCH

Taking into account the individual capabilities of the population, the main means of health and rehabilitation is to determine the level of physical fitness, develop exercises that are suitable for all age groups of the population, rehabilitate diseases and increase the level of physical fitness.

ORGANIZATION OF RESEARCH:

About two thousand residents from different regions of our Republic participated in the pedagogical research. All participants of the study were divided into three groups: young, middle-aged and elderly. The number of participants in all three groups was the same.

Taking into account these problems, we have developed a research design for the popularization of walking in the Scandinavian way using various innovative technologies, and we have used this methodology in practice.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND ITS DISCUSSION:

The analysis of scientific methodical literature and Internet resources on the popularization of the Nordic walking sport showed that in the available information, mainly pictures posted on the Internet were used to popularize the Nordic walking sport. Their main influence is only for young people who are active on the Internet. To solve this problem, we used several methods that are equally suitable for all (see Figure 1).

We divided and arranged the popularization of Scandinavian walking sport in our country as follows:

1. Development of the concept of population health research

- Development of a questionnaire to determine the knowledge of all levels of the population on Nordic walking sports
- Separation of segments of the population that follow a healthy lifestyle and are interested in walking in the Scandinavian way
- Development of Scandinavian walking methodology taking into account the results of this survey.

2. To open special pages in social networks to popularize and promote Nordic walking sport

- Open a channel called "Scandinavian walking" on the Telegram social network and post daily information about this sport.
- Open an account called "Scandinavian walking" on Instagram and Facebook social networks, increase the number of subscribers and constantly post information and videos about Scandinavian walking

3. Organization of educational seminars for the popularization of Scandinavian walking in the district, city and regions

- Organization of seminar trainings with all strata of the population in cooperation with the district, city and regional administration
- To introduce the method of providing information on the positive effects of the Scandinavian walking sport on the human body and teaching walking techniques
- Separation of segments of the population that follow a healthy lifestyle and are interested in walking in the Scandinavian way
- Development of Scandinavian walking methodology taking into account the results of this survey.

4. To open special pages in social networks to popularize and promote the sport of Nordic walking

- Open a channel called "Scandinavian walking" on the Telegram social network and post daily information about this sport.
- Open an account called "Scandinavian walking" on Instagram and Facebook social networks, increase the number of subscribers and constantly post information and videos about Scandinavian walking

5. Organization of educational seminars for the popularization of Scandinavian walking in the district, city and regions

- Organization of seminar trainings with all strata of the population in cooperation with the district, city and regional administration
- To introduce the method of providing information on the positive effects of the Scandinavian walking sport on the human body and teaching walking techniques

This banner, which provides general information about the Nordic walking sport, is equally suitable for people of all age groups. This banner consists of:

1. Correct selection of Scandinavian walking sticks. To choose the right Scandinavian walking sticks, first of all, it is enough to multiply the height by 0.65. In the local method, the optimal position of the stick is obtained when the hand is held at a 90° angle with the ends of the stick touching the ground.
2. "Skan.hod-2" mobile application that teaches Scandinavian walking. This mobile application is placed in the "Play market" program, and this application can be used by people of all ages. A banner designed by us provides instructions on how to download this mobile application.

3. The difference between Nordic walking and other sports. This section of our Nordic walking overview banner clearly shows the difference between Nordic walking and cycling.
4. Scandinavian walking technique. In this section, brief information about the Scandinavian walking technique is given, the correct movement of the legs and hands, and the correct control methods of the Nordic walking sticks are clearly shown.
5. The positive effect of Scandinavian walking on the human body. In this section, it is explained exactly how Nordic walking affects which organ systems and how important Nordic walking is in the proper development of the body.

CONCLUSION:

Today, the deterioration of the health of the population of our country, especially cardiovascular diseases, excess weight, nervousness, and various chronic diseases, puts a number of demands on specialists working in the field of sports.

Although the Nordic walking sport is one of the most important sports in developed countries today, it is important to use the latest innovative technologies to popularize this sport in our country.

Increasing the level of physical development and general physical fitness of the population, as well as the use of new innovative technologies in the effective use of free time of all segments of the population, and the use of special methods in the popularization of Nordic walking, will allow maintaining and strengthening human health, which is the most important and dearest to everyone today.

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